

MEDICAL SCIENCES

COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF MICROBIAL SPECIES IN ACUTE CHOLANGITIS PATIENTS WITH MALIGNANT AND BENIGN OBSTRUCTION

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Abstract

Background. Acute cholangitis is a clinical entity caused by bacterial infection of the biliary system, most common secondary to partial or complete obstruction of the bile duct or hepatic ducts.

Methods. Patients with acute cholangitis admitted to hospital between January 2019 and December 2024. The diagnostic criteria for acute cholangitis were based on Tokyo Guidelines 18.

Results. Of the 244 patients with positive biliary tract disease, 146 had benign disease and 98 had malignant disease. At the species level, *E.coli*, *Klebsiella pneumoniae* were most commonly found Gram-negative bacterial strains in biliary tract infection.

Conclusion. The positive rate in biliary culture was higher in patients with acute cholangitis of a benign cause than with malignant cause.

Keywords: acute cholangitis, microorganism, malignant obstruction, benign obstruction, bile culture

Introduction. Acute cholangitis, is a severe condition that affects the hepatobiliary system, with an associated mortality of 15% if treated with endoscopic biliary drainage, and approximately 50% if untreated. The diagnosis of AC was based, until recently, on the Charcot triad, which uses as diagnostic criteria fever, abdominal pain, and jaundice [1,2].

The microbial spectrum in acute cholangitis has evolved over the years. Initially dominated by *Escherichia coli* and *Klebsiella pneumoniae*, recent studies have reported a diversification in the microbial species involved, including the rise of anaerobic bacteria [3]. This shift in the microbial landscape has important implications for antibiotic therapy, as the efficacy of traditional regimens is increasingly being questioned. The role of cholecystectomy, a common treatment for gallstone-related disease, in altering microbial patterns and resistance profiles in acute cholangitis patients remains underexplored [4].

Cancer patients have a three-time higher risk of death from infection, which is a very common complication in the particular population. Thus, increasing antibiotic resistance in patients with malignant disease can lead to unfavorable outcomes after AC. Although the incidence of bloodstream infection (BSI) in patients with solid tumors is lower than in hematological patients, the majority of studies have focused on patients

with hematological malignancies, while the most frequent source of recurrent BSI seems to be cholangitis. Multi-drug resistance pathogens are an evolving problem in AC, especially in immunocompromised patients [5,6].

Material and methods. This was a retrospective study. Patients with acute cholangitis admitted to a St.Paraskeva medical center, Communal Clinical hospital 8, department of surgery Pustomy Hospital between January 2019 and December 2024.

For the study, acute cholangitis (AC) was diagnosed by adhering to the criteria outlined in the latest clinical guidelines (TG-18). Enrolled participants were categorized into two groups. The variables considered for analysis comprised demographic data: the etiology of infection, the clinical characteristic of the study population (age, gender, signs and symptoms, cholecystectomy, biliary drainage, Tokyo severity score), bacterial identification in bile, and antimicrobial resistance patterns. The study included 4 classes of antibiotic: cephalosporins, fluoroquinolones, carbapenems and penicillin.

Results. A total number of 244 patients were included in study. The etiology of cholangitis was analyzed in table 1.

Table 1

Comparison of etiology between patients with malignant and benign disease

Etiology	Total (n=244)
Benign (n=146)	146 (59.8%)
Cholelithiasis	135 (55.3%)
Benign choledochal stenosis	5 (2%)
Mirizzi syndrome	3 (1.3%)
Liver abscess	3 (1.3%)
Malignant (n=98)	98 (40.2%)
Pancreatic cancer	88 (36%)
Cholangiocarcinoma	5 (2%)
Malignant extrinsic compression	3 (1.3%)
Gallbladder cancer	2 (0.8%)

Table 2 presents the background characteristics of patient, divided into two groups with and without chol-

ecystectomy. The analysis included a total of 244 patients, with 96 who had a history of cholecystectomy and 148 patients who did not go through the procedure.

Table 2

Characteristics of patients with and without cholecystectomy

Variables	Cholecystectomy (n=96)	Non- cholecystectomy (n=148)	p-value
Age (mean \pm SD)	66.5 \pm 12.5	63.7 \pm 11.5	0.062
Sex			0.276
Male	45 (46.9%)	81 (54.7%)	
Female	51 (53.1%)	67 (45.3%)	
Symptoms			
Abdominal pain	75 (78%)	112 (75.7%)	0.704
Jaundice	84 (87.5%)	138 (93.3%)	0.711
Fever and chills	25 (26%)	99 (66.9%)	0.938
ERCP timing			0.755
Emergent (<48H)	48 (50%)	88 (59.5%)	
Urgent (48-72 H)	30 (31.3%)	24 (16.2%)	
Late (>72H)	18 (18.7%)	36 (24.3%)	
Duration of hospitalization stay (median)	7.5 (4.9)	7.3 (5.1)	0.543
Tokyo severity score			0.377
Grade I	36 (37.5%)	66 (44.6%)	
Grade II	42 (43.8%)	46 (31%)	
Grade III	18 (18.7%)	36 (24.4%)	
Etiology of obstruction			0.060
Malignant	42 (42.9%)	56 (37.9%)	
Benign	68 (57.1%)	78 (62.1%)	

Age distribution showed a slightly higher mean age in the cholecystectomy group (66.5years) compared to the non-cholecystectomy group (63.7 years), but this difference was not statistically significant (p-value=0.062). The prevalence of symptoms like abdominal pain, jaundice, and fever and chills were similar in both group, with not significant differences (p-value: 0.704, 0.711, and 0.938, respectively). In terms of ERCP timing, a comparable distribution was observed across emergent, urgent, and late categories in both group (p-value=0.755).

Tokyo severity score, categorized into grades I, II, and III, showed a balanced distribution across both group, with no significant differences observed (p-

value=0.377). A higher percentage of benign causes was observed in the cholecystectomy group (42.9%) compared to the non-cholecystectomy group (37.9%), while malignant causes were common in the non-cholecystectomy group (62.1%) compared to the cholecystectomy group (57.1%), with no statistical significance (p-value=0.060).

C-reactive protein levels were significantly higher in the cholecystectomy group (131 mg/L) compared to the non-cholecystectomy group (111 mg/L), with a p-value of 0.035, suggesting a significantly stronger inflammatory response in the patients who had a history of cholecystectomy (table3).

Table 3

Variables	Cholecystectomy (n=96)	Non- cholecystectomy (n=148)	p-value
WBC	12.4±5.0	12.8±4.4	0.534
CRP	131±75.1	111±86.4	0.035
Total bilirubin	8.1±5.5	7.1±4.9	0.039
PLT	261.2±86.9	281.3±99.8	0.118
INR	3.4±1.4	2.8±1.6	0.109

According to the Tokyo guidelines of 2018, monomicrobial growth was found more in patients with mild severity (20%), followed by moderate severity (15%) and the severe grade (7%), as seen in table 4. Monomicrobial growth was the most encountered (42%) in comparison with sterile (28%) or polymicrobial cultures (two bacteria – 25% or three bacteria –

5%). Cultures were positive in 186 of 244 bile specimens (76%), most of them (115/186, 62%) having a benign etiology for the acute obstruction of the main biliary duct; 41% of patients (77/186) had a malignant etiology of acute cholangitis.

Table 4

Tokyo grade	Grade I (n=102)	Grade II (n=88)	Grade III (n=54)	Significance
Sterile	24 (10%)	28 (12%)	15 (6%)	0.929
1 bacterium	48 (20%)	35 (15%)	18 (7%)	
2 bacteria	25 (11%)	20 (8%)	17 (6.5%)	
3 bacteria	5 (2%)	5 (2%)	4 (1.5%)	

Table 5 describes a detailed comparison of isolated microorganisms from bile cultures between patients with malignant and benign obstruction causes. The most frequently encountered in bile culture were Gram negative bacteria, including E.coli, Klebsiella

spp., Pseudomonas spp. and Citrobacter. The most frequently encountered Gram-positive bacteria was Enterococcus.

Table 5

Isolated microorganism from bile cultures	Total (n=186)	Malignant (n=77)	Benign (n=115)	Significance
Gram-negative microorganism				
E.coli	88/186 (47.3%)	41 (53.2%)	47 (40.9%)	0.004
Klebsiella spp.	49/186 (26.3%)	21 (27.3%)	28 (24.3%)	0.796
Pseudomonas spp.	28/186 (15%)	15 (19.5%)	13 (11.3%)	0.669
Enterobacter spp.	9/186 (4.8%)	3 (3.9%)	6 (5.2%)	0.845
Acinetobacter spp.	5/186 (2.7%)	2 (2.6%)	3 (2.6%)	0.104
Citrobacter spp.	15/186 (8%)	7 (9%)	8 (7%)	0.725
Gram positive microorganism				
Enterococcus spp.	45/186 (24%)	22 (28.6%)	23 (20%)	0.514
Streptococcus spp.	2/186 (1%)	1 (1.3%)	1 (0.9%)	0.218
Staphylococcus spp.	4/186 (2.2%)	2 (2.6%)	2 (1.7%)	0.658

Discussion. Based on the findings, the current study carries significant implications for the clinical management of acute cholangitis patients with malignant and benign obstructions by providing valuable insights into the microbial species and their antimicrobial resistance patterns in these patients groups [7,8]. Among the studies key findings, it was observed that E.coli was the most frequently encountered bacteria in bile cultures, with a higher prevalence in patients with benign disease than malignant disease.

Conclusion. The positive rate in biliary culture was higher in patients with acute cholangitis of a benign cause than with malignant cause.

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